
The Effect of Marine Algae Extract on the Rate of Calcium Oxalate Dissolution

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Abstract The study aims to investigate the impact of marine algae in the process of extracting calcium oxalates through the decomposition of calcium oxalate monohydrate (COM) crystals when the presence of different marine algae. There are three extracts of marine algae that were studied sargassum (SA), Ultra Lactuca (UL) within different temperatures at 37°C, I=0.15 mol dm⁻³, and pH=6.5. The results of the study showed a decrease in the percentage of additives due to the dissolution of calcium oxalate crystals when concentrations of additives lower than 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³. Also, results showed that an increase of additives concentrations on the surfaces of calcium oxalate crystals decreases the rate of dissolution of the crystals due to chemical absorption.

The study revealed that values of reaction (n=2), active energy 7.18 Kcal/mol, and Langmuir- isotherm. Constants values using SA, UL, and EN 7.1, 5.9, and 4.57 × 10⁵ dm³ mol⁻¹. The chemical adsorption of (KI) under-saturation ($\sigma = 0.09$) and the order of inhibition were: SA > UL > the US.

Keywords Calcium oxalate, dissolution, marine algae, Additive, Adsorption inhibition

Introduction

Researchers revealed that 50% of kidney stones contain calcium oxalate (CaOx), and calcium phosphate (Caph). Calcium Oxalate (CaOx) is one of the ionic chemical compounds that contain all the oxalate and calcium ions [1]. Calcium Oxalate is an ionic compound formed from the Calcium and Oxalate ions.

Dissolution of crystals calcium oxalate is of particular importance in biological systems. ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), is known for its ability to dissolve calcium oxalate crystals but has not previously been used in the clinical management of urolithiasis because of toxic side effects [2].

Among the calcium salts that make kidney stones are the monohydrate and dihydrate oxalate calcium [3].

Calcium oxalate crystals are characterized by a complex shape with a group of atoms that vary in size and are associated with foods that contain oxalic acid [4].

Materials and Methods

Algae were collected from the Red Sea coast in Jeddah. Pyrex glassware chemicals with analytical grad utilized. The triple distillation method is applied to filter and purify water by deionizing.

Composition of crystal

Calcium oxalate seeds were prepared by adding one liter of 0.1 M calcium chloride solutions to one liter of sodium oxalate solution (0.1 M) at 298 K at a rate of 250 mL per half an hour. The seed crystals stored for one month., then were re-filtered and washed further with deionized distilled water and. The seeds were then filtered and dried. The seed material was then subject to x-ray powder diffraction studies, scanning electron microscope, and IR diffraction. In the process of preparing calcium oxalate seeds, the added calcium chloride solutions were 1 liter of 0.1 M to the sodium oxalate solution (0.1 M) at 298 K at an average of 250 mL through half an hour interval that was specified for the preparation process. Then the seeds were cleaned and washed with distilled water. The seeds were dried after being cleaned and then seed powder exposed to x-rays, electron microscopes, and infrared rays.

Table 1: X-ray powder diffraction

No. of peaks	2θ	d (Å)	I / I_0
1	15.1	5.87	67
2	24.6	3.60	100
3	30.4	2.95	53
4	36.2	2.50	39
5	38.5	2.34	74

Extraction and isolation of different extracts from Algae freely

Extraction process is applied to extract soluble materials such as soluble fats, additives, and secondary compounds components. material. Aqueous extract algae freely, they were made by using (Soxhlet system HT, 1043. Extraction Unit) made in Elveden.

Preparation of extract solution

The preparation of aqueous extract was made by the reduction of filled solutions to achieve various concentrations. The solid reflectance measurements were measured at room temperature in the UV-Vis.

Results and Discussion

The calcium oxalate formation in solution in both analytical and biological fields importance points to the need for quantitative studies of the ionic interactions in solutions of this electrolyte and also the kinetics of its dissolution and crystal growth. Studies have proven the presence of calcium oxalate is found in all renal and bladder stones [5].

The decay of Calcium Oxalate Monohydrate (COM) at the presence of aqueous extracts in some kinds of algae

Urinary stones are made up of inorganic crystals and organic matrix. The major composition of crystals is calcium oxalate, the total mass percentage of it is about 70 – 80 % in urinary stones. Thermodynamically stable COM is much more common in stones and is not easy to be expelled out from the body [6]. In our research, we show the effect of some extracts on the dissolution of calcium oxalate.

Impact of various algae extracts in dissolution attribution

Some types of algae and its extracts within dissolution rate include:

Sargassum species-genus are large canopy-forming marine brown algae. These algae are of two species, namely *fluitans* and *natans*. The extraction of **sargassum** contains carbohydrates, protein, amino acids, iodine, bromine, vitamins, and substance of stimulatory and antibiotic nature.

U. Lactuca” alga powder was characterized by fibers content, proteins, minerals, proteins, and lipids. *Ulva Lactuca*, contains high levels of sulfate, Vitamin A, B2, B12, and C and is rich in γ -tocopherol.

Ulva sp is a green seaweed (Chlorophyta) and is a marine seaweed present almost year-round.

Ulva sp besides chlorophyll and some minerals it is also containing functional groups such as amino, hydroxyl, carboxyl, and sulfate.

Effect of aqueous extracts of SA

Figure 1: Plots of the amount of calcium dissolve against time without additive (a) and in presence of SA (b)

Figure 2: Plots of SA/10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³ and R/10⁻¹⁰ mol min⁻¹ m⁻²

Figure 3: Plots of decay rate under saturation utilizing measurements of U.V visible spectra.

Figure 4: Plots of $-\log R$ against $-\log \sigma$ for dissolution of COM at 37 °C

Figure 5: Plots of the amount of calcium dissolve

Figure 6: Plots of the amount of calcium dissolution against time without additive (a) and in presence of UL (b) In presence of algae

Figure 7: Plots $[UL]^{-1} / 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $R / 10^{-10} \text{ mol min}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$

Conclusion

Sargassum (SA), Ulva Lactuca (UL), and Ulva Sp (US) are a good inhibitor in degradation crystals of calcium oxalate. Three kinds of algae obtained an inhibition effect but by different percentages. Sargassum gets the best inhibition rate then Ulva Lactuca then Ulva sp.

Various extracts from Sargassum species that influenced the dissolution of calcium oxalate crystals, resulted in essential, where Sargassum could confirm effective functional ingredients for pharmaceuticals for the medication and prevention of several diseases such as urinary stones due to its ability to inhibit calcium oxalate crystallization properties.

Ulva Lactuca is a current green alga. Ulva extracts presented potential antibacterial, hypolipidemic, cardioprotective, and chemoprotective activities. Ulva Lactuca is rich in phenolic constituents, which offering a potential utility as an antioxidant candidate. *This reason makes* Ulva Lactuca is generally used for the treatment of infectious diseases and oxidative stress-related disorders. The finding of the present work confirmed that the seaweed extract of U. Lactuca L. can be recommended as an antifungal agent in preparing eco-friendly disinfectant. Genus Ulva has a beneficial impact on productivity and health because of its role in plant and animal systems by modulating cellular signaling processes.

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